

Survival Analysis and Maintenance Policies for a Series System, With Highly Censored Data

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Key Words: Total Time on Test (TTT), Censored Data, Survival Analysis, Kaplan-Meier Estimator, Piecewise Exponential Estimator, Optimal Age Replacement.

SUMMARY & CONCLUSIONS

This paper considers the problem of estimating the survival function from a large set of sampling data subject to high levels of random censoring on the right. The system under study consists of a series arrangement of four functional subsystems. Each of the functional subsystems consists of a collection of independent components in series. The system does not have redundant components. This study aims to simulate a series arrangement of four unique components and compare the performance of the Kaplan Meier Estimator (KME), the Piecewise Exponential Estimator (PEXE) and the Maximum Likelihood Estimator (MLE) in estimating the survivor functions for the system as well as individual components under high levels of random censorship. Monte Carlo analysis is used to compare total time on test plots and optimal age replacement times determined using the KME and PEXE methods. This study extends the work of Klefsjo and Westberg (Ref. 10) by considering the estimation of survivor functions and optimal age replacement periods under higher levels of random censorship (up to 90%). The effect of such high censoring is that both the survivor curve and the optimal replacement time are generally, and sometimes severely, underestimated at the component level but not necessarily at the system level. Further studies will examine the trade-offs in using system level vs. component level data to make maintenance decisions for highly censored samples.

1. INTRODUCTION

The objective of this study is to simulate the data for an Air Force system which is subject to very high amounts of random censoring. The system under study is currently operating in the field and a relatively large amount of operational data is available ($n=2500^+$ observations). Approximately 80% of the available data is right censored. In this study we want to explore a variety of techniques for accurately estimating the survival function from censored data as well as to determine optimal age replacement strategies for the system. In order to quantify the error and determine the adequacy of a proposed

technique a simulation study is performed.

A series system of four components each having a continuous increasing failure rate (IFR) is modeled. The life distributions for the four components in this study are Weibull with increasing failure rates. These distributions are chosen to approximate those of the actual system. A sample size of size $n = 2500$ is used in each simulation. The proportions of random censoring examined in this study are approximately 70%, 80%, and 90%.

An exponential distribution is used to model the censoring distribution. The amount of random censoring is controlled by varying the mean of this exponential distribution. Each of the three proportions of censoring are analyzed by looking at survival curves based on the KME, PEXE, and MLE estimates and TTT-plots constructed from the KME and the PEXE. TTT-plots are then used to determine the optimal replacement time. Each of these replacement times are compared with the true optimal replacement time. Analysis is performed on the system as a whole as well as on individual components.

2.0 THE KAPLAN-MEIER ESTIMATOR

Often in life testing it is not possible to observe the failure time of every item on test. The items for which the exact failure time cannot be observed are said to be censored. If all that is known about the censored item is the amount of time that it was observed to be functioning, then the item is right censored. Consider n items placed on test at time $t = 0$ and observed until failure or withdrawal. Order the observed failure and censor times so that $0 \leq t_1 \leq t_2 \leq \dots \leq t_n$. The Kaplan-Meier estimator (KME) of the survivor function $R(t)$ is well known and is defined by

$$\hat{R}_{kme}(t) = \prod_j \frac{n-j}{n-j+1} \quad (1)$$

where j runs through the positive integers for which $t_j \leq t$ and t_j are observed failure times. Notice that this formulation regards $x_{(n)}$ as an observed failure time, even if this may not be the case (Ref. 10).

3.0 THE PIECEWISE EXPONENTIAL ESTIMATOR

A more recently developed estimator for the survivor function for censored data is the Piecewise Exponential Estimator (PEXE). Discussions of the properties of the PEXE as well as a comparison to the KME are given by Kim and Proschan (Ref. 8) and Westberg and Klefsjo (Ref. 10).

The development and rationale for the PEXE are as follows. A set of n new items are placed on test at time $t = 0$ and observed until failure or withdrawal, whichever occurs first. Let x represent observed failure times, w represent withdrawal times, and k be the number of withdrawals between consecutive observed failures. Since both the failure distribution of the item and the censoring distribution are assumed to be continuous distributions, no ties will be considered. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} 0 < w_{1,1} < \dots < w_{1,k_1} < x_1 < w_{2,1} < \dots < w_{2,k_2} < x_2 \\ < \dots < x_{m-1} < w_{m,1} < \dots < w_{m,k_m} < x_m < w_{m+1,1} \\ < \dots < w_{m+1,k_{m+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

An estimate of the failure rate in an interval $(x_{j-1}, x_j]$, where $j = 1, 2, \dots, m$ and $x_0 = 0$, is the number of failures observed in the interval, which is 1, divided by the total time on test in that interval. That is,

$$\hat{r}_j = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^{k_j} (w_{j,i} - x_{j-1}) + \left(n - j + 1 - \sum_{i=1}^j k_i \right) \cdot (x_j - x_{j-1})} \quad (3)$$

This approach fits a constant failure rate to each interval between successive failures which is then used to fit an exponential estimator of the survivor function for each interval. The separate exponential survivor functions are pieced together to form the piecewise exponential estimator of the survivor function up to the m^{th} failure.

$$\hat{R}_{PEXE}(t) = \begin{cases} \exp(-\hat{r}_1 t) & 0 \leq t \leq x_1 \\ \exp(-[\hat{r}_1 x_1 + \hat{r}_2(t - x_1)]) & x_1 < t \leq x_2 \\ \vdots \\ \exp(-[\hat{r}_1 x_1 + \hat{r}_2(x_2 - x_1) + \dots + \hat{r}_i(t - x_{i-1})]) & x_{i-1} < t \leq x_i \\ \vdots \\ \exp(-[\hat{r}_1 x_1 + \hat{r}_2(x_2 - x_1) + \dots + \hat{r}_m(t - x_{m-1})]) & x_{m-1} < t \leq x_m \\ \text{no estimator} & t > x_m \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In order to construct a TTT-plot from the PEXE, an estimate for the survivor function must be made for $t > x_m$. Westberg and Klefsjo (Ref. 10) suggest using a Weibull distribution with shape parameter $\beta = 2$ if there is any indication that the data are from an IFR distribution and a scale parameter given by:

$$\hat{\eta} = \frac{x_m}{\sqrt{-\log(\hat{R}_{PEXE}(x_m))}} \quad (5)$$

Based on prior data from the system that was simulated, a Weibull distribution with shape parameter $\beta = 1.5$ was used in this application.

4.0 THE SCALED TTT-TRANSFORM

The TTT-transform was first used for model identification purposes by Barlow and Campo in 1975 (Ref. 1). First, assume that $F(t)$ is a strictly increasing life distribution function with finite mean, μ . The TTT-transform of $F(t)$ is defined as

$$H^{-1}(v) = n \int_0^{F^{-1}(v)} R(t) dt \quad \text{for } 0 \leq v \leq 1 \quad (6)$$

where

$$F^{-1}(v) = \inf \{ t : F(t) \geq v \} \quad (7)$$

The scaled TTT-transform is obtained by dividing by μ ,

$$\varphi_F(v) = \frac{n}{\mu} \int_0^{F^{-1}(v)} R(t) dt \quad \text{for } 0 \leq v \leq 1 \quad (8)$$

TTT-plots have been used by Bergman (Ref. 2), Bergman and Klefsjo (Ref. 3,4,5) to determine optimal age replacement intervals. Westberg and Klefsjo (Ref. 10,11) have investigated the use of the TTT-plot, including a study on optimal replacement time, with up to 60% censored data constructed from both the KME and the PEXE.

For randomly censored data, a TTT-plot can be constructed using the KME by letting $v_{(i)} = 1 - \hat{R}_{KME}(x_i)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, for the i^{th} ordered failure time and estimating the TTT-transform with

$$\begin{aligned} H_{KME}^{-1}(v_{(i)}) &= n \int_0^{v_{(i)}} \hat{R}_{KME}(u) du \\ &= n \sum_{j=0}^i (x_{(j)} - x_{(j-1)}) \cdot \hat{R}_{KME}(x_{(j-1)}) \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $t_0 = 0$. The TTT-plot is obtained by plotting the coordinates

$$\left\{ v_{(i)}, \frac{\hat{H}^{-1}(v_{(i)})}{\hat{H}^{-1}(v_{(m)})} \right\}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (10)$$

Kaplan and Meier (Ref. 7) show the KME to be a strongly consistent estimator of the underlying distribution function. Therefore, the TTT-plot based on the KME converges to the scaled TTT-transform $\varphi_F(v)$ as n approaches infinity.

The TTT-plot based on the PEXE is constructed in a similar fashion by letting $v_{(i)} = 1 - \hat{R}_{PEXE}(x_i)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, m$, and inserting the piecewise exponential survivor function into the TTT-transform as follows

$$H_{PEXE}^{-1}(v_{(i)}) = n \int_0^{v_{(i)}} \hat{R}_{PEXE}(u) du$$

$$= n \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^i \frac{-1}{\hat{r}_j} \left[\exp\left(-\sum_{k=1}^i \hat{r}_k (x_{(k)} - x_{(k-1)})\right) - \exp\left(-\sum_{k=0}^{i-1} \hat{r}_k (x_{(k)} - x_{(k-1)})\right) \right] \right\} \quad (11)$$

where $x_0 = x_{-1} = 0$ and $r_0 = 0$.

If x_m is not the last observation (i.e. if there are withdrawals after the last failure) then a final segment should be added to the TTT-plot (Ref. 10). If there is evidence that the failure distribution is in the IFR class, then use a Weibull distribution with some shape parameter greater than 1. In this simulation, shape parameter $\beta = 1.5$ was used. The final term added to the sequence above is

$$H_{PEXE}^{-1}(v_{(m+1)}) = n \cdot \frac{\hat{\eta}}{\beta} \left(\frac{x_{(m)}}{\hat{\eta}} \right)^{\beta-1} \exp\left[-\left(\frac{x_{(m)}}{\hat{\eta}}\right)^\beta\right] \quad (12)$$

For the TTT-plot in this case it is necessary to set $v_{(x_{(m+1)})} = 1$. Then plot the coordinates

$$\left\{ v_{(x_{(i)})}, \frac{\hat{H}_{PEXE}^{-1}(v_{(i)})}{\hat{H}_{PEXE}^{-1}(v_{(m+1)})} \right\}, i = 1, 2 \dots m. \quad (13)$$

If the last observed time does correspond to a failure, then plot the coordinates are given by:

$$\left\{ \frac{v_{(x_{(i)})}}{v_{(x_{(m)})}}, \frac{\hat{H}_{PEXE}^{-1}(v_{(i)})}{\hat{H}_{PEXE}^{-1}(x_{(m)})} \right\}, i = 1, 2 \dots m. \quad (14)$$

5.0 OPTIMAL REPLACEMENT TIME

Bergman (Ref. 2) pioneered the use of the TTT-plot for estimating optimal replacement time. The general idea is to use the optimal replacement time to formulate a maintenance strategy in which the component is returned to "as good as new" condition upon failure or at the optimal replacement time, whichever occurs first.

Using censored samples, Westberg and Klefsjo (Ref. 10) compared the optimal replacement times obtained from the TTT-plot based on the KME to the times obtained from the TTT-plot constructed from the PEEXE. They concluded in the study that the PEEXE method performed at least as well as the KME method, especially when censoring was heavy.

Let $c + K$ be the total cost to replace an item that has failed and c be the cost of a planned replacement when the item has reached a certain age t_0 . Essentially, c is the cost of replacing the item and K is an additional cost or consequence that is incurred by the failure of the item. In order to minimize the

cost per unit time in the long run, it is necessary to find the value of t_0 that minimizes

$$C(t_0) = \frac{c + (k \cdot F(t_0))}{\int_0^{t_0} (1 - F(t)) dt} \quad (15)$$

Bergman and Klefsjo (Ref. 3) discuss a graphical solution to this problem via the TTT-plot. The optimal value t_0 is found by plotting $-c/K$ on the horizontal axis, drawing the line with the maximum slope from the coordinate $(-c/K, 0)$ to the TTT-plot, and identifying the observed failure time $t_{(i)}$ that corresponds to the coordinates of the point of contact. If the line with the largest slope connects $(-c/K, 0)$ to $(1, 1)$, then $t_0 = \infty$ and no preventive maintenance is recommended.

6.0 SIMULATION STUDY

Our model consists of a series arrangement of four components having Weibull distributions. The reliability function for an item with a Weibull distribution is

$$R(t) = \exp\left[-\left(\frac{t}{\eta}\right)^\beta\right] \quad t > 0 \quad (16)$$

A reliability block diagram showing the shape (β) and scale (η) parameters used as well as the corresponding mean (μ) for each Weibull population is shown below.

Figure 1. System Reliability Block Diagram

The reliability function for this series system of independent components is given by the product of the reliability functions of each component and is given below.

$$R_{SYS}(t) = \exp\{-[(t/\eta_1)^{\beta_1} + (t/\eta_2)^{\beta_2} + (t/\eta_3)^{\beta_3} + (t/\eta_4)^{\beta_4}]\} \quad t > 0 \quad (17)$$

Suppose this system is subject to random censoring generated by an exponential distribution with parameter q defined by the distribution function

$$G(t) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\theta}\right), \quad t \geq 0 \quad (18)$$

The expected proportion of censoring at the system level is

$$q = \int_0^{\infty} R_{SYS}(t) dG(t) \quad (19)$$

Using the Weibull shape and scale parameters given above, the expected proportions of censoring are shown for certain

values of q in the table below.

Table 1. Censoring Parameters

q	0.70	0.80	0.90
θ	650	410	215
for Exponential			

A Monte Carlo simulation with 1000 replications of sample size $n = 2500$ was used to compare the PEXE to the KME. All simulations were carried out in Matlab version 4.2c on a Sun Sparc Station 10. Each simulation took approximately 25 hrs. All ML estimates were obtained using Weibull++ version 5.0 beta (Ref. 12).

7.0 RESULTS

The PEXE and the KME are compared by examining the mean and standard deviation of the area between the TTT-plot constructed using each method and the true TTT-transform. Further, the mean and standard deviation of the difference between the optimal replacement time given by each method to the true optimal replacement time is found. Individual component analysis as well as system level analysis is examined for each degree of censoring.

In the tables below, the mean and standard deviation of the area between the TTT-plot and the TTT-transform are displayed for the system as well as for the components for the three different censoring levels.

Table 2 System Level Comparison

q	PEXE	KME
0.70	-0.0100 (0.0194)	0.0074 (0.0166)
0.80	-0.0068 (0.0252)	0.0241 (0.0254)
0.90	0.0241 (0.0351)	0.0740 (0.0393)

Table 3a Component Level Comparison

	Component 1		Component 2	
Q	PEXE	KME	PEXE	KME
0.70	0.0560 (.0363)	0.1185 (.0415)	0.0489 (.0318)	0.1204 (.0428)
0.80	0.0742 (.0360)	0.1449 (.0460)	0.0572 (.0338)	0.1420 (.0472)
0.90	0.0786 (.0361)	0.1725 (.0529)	0.0512 (.0332)	0.1564 (.0550)

Table 3 Component Level Comparison (cont.)

	Component 3		Component 4	
q	PEXE	KME	PEXE	KME
0.70	0.0338 (.0333)	0.1049 (.0444)	0.0216 (.0324)	0.0986 (.0436)
0.80	0.0411 (.0335)	0.1267 (.0474)	0.0241 (.0329)	0.1174 (.0501)
0.90	0.0313 (.0324)	0.1389 (.0563)	0.0065 (.0337)	0.1231 (.0576)

A negative mean in the tables above indicates that the TTT-plot underestimated the true TTT-transform while positive means resulted from cases where the TTT-plot overestimated the TTT-transform. The KME TTT-plot overestimated the TTT-transform in all cases, on the average, whereas the PEXE TTT-plot underestimated in about half the cases and overestimated in the other half. Both the mean and standard deviation of the difference in the area under the TTT-plot versus the TTT-transform are smaller for the PEXE in all cases except for the 70% censoring case at the system level, which is shown graphically in Figure 2.

Additionally, in the Monte Carlo simulation, the optimal replacement time is obtained from the KME TTT-plot and the PEXE TTT-plot for values of c/K set at 0.10, 0.25, and 0.50 at each of the three levels of censoring considered. The estimated optimal replacement time is then compared to the true optimal replacement time obtained from the TTT-transform. The mean differences in optimal replacement times are tabled below for the system and component 1 of the system. A negative mean difference indicates that the estimated optimal replacement time is less than the true optimal replacement time, on the average. Graphical illustrations of the system TTT-plots used to find the optimal replacement time for 70% censoring are shown in Figures 3, 4, and 5

Table 4. System Level Replacement Analysis

q		$c/K=0.10$	$c/K=0.25$	$c/K=0.50$
0.70	PEXE	37.4	192.3	-156.9
	KME	41.1	177.9	-157.8
0.80	PEXE	128.3	151.3	-624.3
	KME	118.2	107.2	-581.0
0.90	PEXE	144.6	-219.6	-1177.5
	KME	87.4	-288.8	-1215.9

Table 5 Component One Replacement Analysis

q		$c/K=0.10$	$c/K=0.25$	$c/K=0.50$
0.70	PEXE	-232.8	-3135.4	-11431.7
	KME	-445.9	-3286.0	-11506.6
0.80	PEXE	-651.0	-3672.1	-12027.2
	KME	-804.3	-3781.0	-12079.9
0.90	PEXE	-1185.9	-4318.0	-12669.5
	KME	-1281.8	-4379.6	-12749.3

The resulting mean differences for components 2, 3 and 4 are not given explicitly in this paper but are very similar to those obtained for component 1. One result that stands out in the tables above is that the PEXE and the KME are missing the true optimal replacement time in the same way for each case examined. At the system level, both methods overestimate the true optimal replacement time when $c/K = 0.10$ and both underestimate the true optimal replacement time when $c/K = 0.50$. Results are somewhat mixed as to which method provides a better overall estimate of the true optimal replacement time for the overall system.

However, at the component level both methods underestimate the true optimal replacement time in every instance for all four components. As seen in the table above for component 1, the amount of underestimation increases as the proportion of censoring increases and as the ratio c/K increases. This trend is present in the analysis of all four components. Furthermore, the optimal replacement time determined from the PEXE TTT-plot is always closer to the true optimal replacement time than the optimal replacement time determined from the KME TTT-plot.

CONCLUSIONS

Very high rates of censoring cause the KME, the PEXE, as well as the MLE of the survivor function to significantly underestimate the true survivor function at the component level. This is shown in Figure 6 for component 2 at 70% censoring. This underestimation of the survivor function and consequent overestimation of the hazard rate coincides with the underestimation of the optimal replacement time. In other words, the higher the proportion of censoring, the greater the errors (on the low side) in estimating optimal replacement time. This means that preventive maintenance is recommended by the estimation methods above much sooner than is necessary when censoring rates are in the 70% to 90% range.

However, each estimator mentioned above provides a relatively good estimate of the true survivor curve at the system level for each degree of censoring. An example is shown in Figure 7 for the 70% censoring case. This is commensurate with the result that the error in estimating the optimal replacement time for the system is really not significantly large for either the PEXE or the KME method. Further studies will examine the trade-offs in using system level vs. component level data to make maintenance decisions for highly censored samples.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by ASC/YA (H6496005). The authors wish to thank Mr. Paul Guglielmoni and Mr. Norm Smith for their support. A special thanks goes to Dr. John Crown for his comments on the first draft of this paper.

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Figure 3 System TTT-Plot, Uncensored

Figure 2 Component 1 TTT-Transform, 70% Censored

Figure 4 System KME TTT-Plot, 70% Censored

Figure 5 System PEXE TTT-Plot, 70% Censored

Figure 7. System Survivor Function, 70% Censored

Figure 6 Component 1 Survivor Function, 70% Censored